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Publication Outcomes Doctoral Dissertations in Teaching Turkish as a Foreign Language Field

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Abstract

This research determines the rates of converting doctoral dissertations into publications, types of publications (book, book chapter, journal article), and the status of publications according to indexes in the field of teaching Turkish as a foreign language. For this purpose, first, doctoral dissertations in this field until 2020 were identified through the keywords in the Council of Higher Education Thesis Centre database. Then, the status of the dissertations being converted into publications was investigated. The sample of the research consisted of 98 doctoral dissertations. Document analysis, a qualitative research method, was employed in the research. According to the findings of the research, most doctoral dissertations were completed in 2018. Hacettepe University, Gazi University, and Atatürk University are the universities with the highest number of doctoral dissertations in the relevant field. It was also detected that 28% of the doctoral dissertations in the research sample were not converted into any publication, and articles were mostly preferred (81%) in the conversion of doctoral dissertations into publications. Articles were mostly published in journals indexed in the TR index (61%). According to the results of the research, it can be suggested that the quality of doctoral dissertations in the field of teaching Turkish as a foreign language should be reviewed, and publications in internationally recognized journals should be encouraged.

Keywords: Teaching Turkish as a Foreign Language, Doctoral Dissertations, Publications from Doctoral Dissertations

1. Introduction

The doctoral dissertation, which is the most important step of postgraduate education, can be seen as a turning point for researchers to become scientists. To have been awarded a doctorate degree, publishing academic studies based on their dissertation is automatically viewed as the next step for most new graduates. These are in the form of converting the entire dissertation into a book, converting the dissertation into a journal article or splitting it into several articles, and using an aspect of a dissertation in an edited book.

It is not easy to obtain a dissertation published as a book, book chapter, or an article without making major revisions to it because a dissertation differs from these in many ways (Bowen, 2010; Paltridge, 2017; Paltridge & Starfield,

2020). The length of a dissertation is unlimited, but the length of a book is strategically controlled for marketability. A dissertation has a few long chapters, but a book has several chapters of readable length (Germano, 2013). Similarly, publishing an academic article based on a dissertation “is not just a matter of cutting and pasting it” (Paltridge & Starfield, 2020, p. 157) or “simply a matter of summarizing” (Bowen, 2010, p. 875). There are, obviously, fundamental differences in “the content, format, and length of a journal article” (Bowen, 2010, p. 865) or “goal and objectives” (Pollard, 2004, p. 2) compared to a dissertation. Mesquita (2018) lists some of these differences as follows: A dissertation meets academic requirements, is reviewed by a director and a supervisor committee member, has some chapters, no word limits, a table of contents, is lengthy research of literature, whereas an article meets journalistic standards, is reviewed by a panel of blind reviewers, has sections, word limits, manuscript format, is succinct research of literature. Another key difference between a dissertation and an article is the audience. It will therefore mainly go unread aside by examiners, supervisors, other doctorate students, peers, and perhaps rare scholars, making it exceedingly unlikely to affect practice or thought (Tribe & Tunariu, 2016). It is important in terms of scientific communication, that dissertations are converted into publications to reach broader audiences. The publication of a dissertation in a peer-reviewed journal contributes to a more accessible, permanent, and rapid dissemination of research results. Journals serve as hubs of scientific thinking and forums for idea exchange since they have evolved into the fundamental tool for scientific communication. In the form of explicit guidelines for academic discourse, ethics, and accountability for the calibre of research, they have also influenced the mindsets of generations of researchers (Kachniewska, 2019). Therefore, an unpublished dissertation in a peer-viewed journal may become just “shelf-bending” research, sitting in your university library and slowly bending a shelf over the years (Dunleavy, 2003, p. 227).

Articles derived from dissertations supply an excellent database from which to disseminate, share and convey new ideas, information, or concepts. Dissemination of a dissertation through peer-reviewed journals is an indicator of the scientific value of a dissertation and of the acceptability of its content by the international scientific community as to whether it has been published in a peer-reviewed journal (Nieminen et al., 2007). An unpublished dissertation is a lost opportunity for both the graduate and the scientific community at large because research findings reported in dissertations are less likely to be cited in academic journals (Thomas, 2015), and the nonpublication of a dissertation can also be detrimental to the advancement of scientific knowledge in other ways (Evans, Amaro, Herbert, Blossom & Roberts, 2018).

When we look at the issue of producing publications from doctoral dissertations from the perspective of Turkey, it is seen that this situation is a compulsory requirement. In Turkey, it has become compulsory for scientists who want to pursue an academic career after doctoral education to produce at least one publication from their doctoral theses as of December 2016 by the Turkish Interuniversity Board (Interuniversity Board, 2016). Additionally, some universities in Turkey (Gazi University Postgraduate, 2019; Bursa Uludağ University Postgraduate, 2020) encourage the production of publications from doctoral theses by accepting at least one scientific article related to the student’s doctoral thesis topic published or accepted for publication in national/international refereed journals as a condition for going in for doctoral thesis defense. In the workshop on improving doctoral education organized by the Council of Higher Education (CoHE) in Turkey in 2022, recommendations such as encouraging students to convert their theses into publications, evaluating publishing from the dissertation together with the supervisor, rewarding qualified publications produced within the scope of the dissertation, and making it compulsory to publish at least one article in international indexed journals related to the doctoral dissertation for graduation increase the importance of producing publications from doctoral dissertations (CoHE, 2022).

Recently, there has been a growing body of literature that has examined postgraduate theses in the field of teaching Turkish as a foreign language (TTFL). The majority of these articles have focused on the trends of postgraduate theses (Baki, 2019; Çelebi, Ergül, Büsra & Mutlu, 2019; Kahtalı & Günata, 2021; Karagöz & Şeref, 2021; Kılıç, 2022; Maden & Önal, 2021). In these articles, postgraduate theses were analyzed in terms of the year of publication, supervisor titles, method, design, subject areas, etc., by content analysis. These articles are important in terms of describing the productivity, tendencies, and evolution of scientific and research activity in the relevant field. However, to date, far too little attention has been given to publications derived from dissertations in the TTFL field. It is also significant to describe the rates of converting doctoral theses in this field into publications, types of publications (book, book chapter, journal article), and the status of publications according to indexes. It

should be noted that this research does not aim to evaluate doctoral students, their supervisors, published or unpublished doctoral dissertations and doctoral programs or universities, nor does it support the publication of all doctoral dissertations regardless of their quality. Rather, this research aims to draw attention by shedding light on the rates of publication of doctoral dissertations in the field of TTFL, publication preferences and the status of publications according to indexes. It is thought that increasing research on the quality and publishing of doctoral dissertations in the relevant field will contribute to the quality of doctoral education, dissertations and the productivity of doctoral students. It is also thought that this research is the first research in the related field and will fill the gap in the literature. This research is important in terms of guiding researchers by revealing the trends in publications from doctoral dissertations in the related field, evaluating and self-criticizing doctoral theses and guiding future studies. In this framework, in the research, an answer to the main question “What is the status of publications produced from doctoral dissertations in the field of teaching Turkish as a foreign language?” was sought.

2. Method

2.1 Research Design

In this research, a qualitative research method, document analysis, was employed to identify the publications produced from doctoral dissertations in the field of TTFL. Like other methods used in qualitative research, document analysis requires the examination and interpretation of data to make sense, to create an understanding of the subject matter and to develop empirical knowledge (Corbin & Strauss, 2008). In this research, TTFL dissertations and publications produced from these dissertations were collected, systematically analyzed and evaluated.

2.2 Data Collection

The data collection process in this study consisted of two stages. In the first stage, it was oriented toward the identification of doctoral dissertations. For this purpose, the Turkey Council of Higher Education Thesis Centre database was used as a data source. On this platform, on August 30, 2022, the query terms “Turkish as a foreign language”, “teaching Turkish to foreigners”, “teaching Turkish as a second language” and “Turkish for foreigners” were entered in the search section using the advanced search tab. The doctorate was selected as the thesis type, and all dissertations with or without permission until 2020 were scanned. A total of 108 doctoral dissertations were identified in the search query. The Turkish and English names, universities, author and supervisor names of the dissertations were recorded by the researcher.

The second stage of the data collection process was to detect the publications produced from doctoral dissertations. Doctoral dissertation names were queried in the Web of Science (<http://apps.webofknowledge.com/>), ERIC (<https://eric.ed.gov/>), Google Scholar, and TR Index (<https://trdizin.gov.tr/>) databases in English or Turkish. The query process of the databases commenced on September 3, 2020, and query scanning was completed on September 30, 2020. Considering that the name of the thesis and the study converted into a publication might not have the same name, the query was continued by typing the name of the author and/or thesis supervisor into the databases. With the idea that a part of the dissertation might be converted into a publication, the personal page of the dissertation author in the academic data systems of universities (<https://akademik.yok.gov.tr/AkademikArama/>) and Google Scholar, Researchgate, Academia, Sobiad and Scopus user profiles were checked. An e-mail was sent to a total of 38 thesis authors whose publications could not be identified in all scans, and information was obtained on whether any publications were produced from their theses. As data could not be obtained from 10 thesis authors to whom e-mails were sent, the research sample consisted of 98 doctoral dissertations. Conference papers produced from doctoral dissertations and publications that are not stated to be produced from doctoral dissertations are excluded in the research.

2.3 Data analysis

The identified publications were analyzed by content analysis, which is the process of organizing information into categories related to the central research questions (Bowen, 2009). In the classification of the identified publications, the publication criterion related to graduate theses prepared by the Turkish Interuniversity Board for associate professor candidates in the basic field of educational sciences was used as a reference. According to these criteria, books were divided into two groups: books published by well-known international and national publishers. Similarly, book chapters were divided into two groups as chapters in books published by international and national publishers. The articles were classified into four groups: articles published in journals indexed in the SSCI, SCI, SCI-Expanded and AHCI indexes, international field indexes (Australian Education Index, British Education Index, Journals Indexed in ERIC, Education Full Text, ESCI), TR index and international indexes (SCOPUS, EBSCO, DOAJ, MLA, Index Copernicus, etc.). The identified books and book chapters were sorted into groups by checking whether the publishing houses in which they were published had international or national publishing status. Articles were categorized by verifying the indexes of the journals in which they were published. Descriptive statistics such as percentage, average and frequency were utilized to present the data using the SPSS-18 program.

3. Results

The results of the research are presented below in order of the year of acceptance of the doctoral dissertations, the university where they were conducted, the rate of dissertations converted into publications, the types of publications and the indexes of the publications. The approval years of the 98 doctoral dissertations included in the research sample are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Distribution of dissertations by year

2002	1
2004	1
2010	1
2011	1
2012	1
2014	5
2015	8
2016	8
2017	6
2018	21
2019	28
2020	17
Total	98

As Table 1 indicates, 28 (28.6%) of the dissertations were completed in 2019, 21 (21.4%) in 2018, and 17 (17.3%) in 2020. Eight (16.4%) dissertations were completed in 2015 and 2016, 6 (6.1%) in 2017, and 5 (5.1%) in 2014. A dissertation completed in 2002, 2004, 2010, 2011, and 2012 (5%) was included in the research sample. It is concluded that the 98 theses included in the research sample were conducted in 19 different universities. The universities where the dissertations were conducted are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Distribution of dissertations by universities

<i>Universities</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
Hacettepe University	26	26,5
Gazi University	19	19,4
Atatürk University	13	13,3
Inönü University	7	7,1
Çanakkale Onsekiz Mart University	7	7,1
Sakarya University	6	6,1

Erciyes University	3	3,1
Dokuz Eylül University	2	2,0
Marmara University	2	2,0
Ankara University	2	2,0
Bolu Abant İzzet Baysal University	2	2,0
Hatay Mustafa Kemal University	2	2,0
Selçuk University	1	1,0
İstanbul University	1	1,0
Fırat University	1	1,0
Necmettin Erbakan University	1	1,0
Eskişehir Osmangazi University	1	1,0
Muğla Sıtkı Koçman University	1	1,0
Yıldız Teknik University	1	1,0
Total	98	100,0

Table 2 reveals that 26 (26.5%) dissertations were conducted at Hacettepe University, 19 (14%) at Gazi University, 13 (13.3%) at Atatürk University, 7 (7.1%) each at Çanakkale Onsekiz Mart University and İnönü University, 6 (6.1%) at Sakarya University, and 3 (3.1%) at Erciyes University. At Dokuz Eylül University, Ankara University, Marmara University, Bolu Abant İzzet Baysal University, and Hatay Mustafa Kemal University, 2 (2.0%) doctoral dissertations were conducted at Selçuk University, Istanbul University, Fırat University, Necmettin Erbakan University, Eskişehir Osmangazi University, Muğla Sıtkı Koçman University, and Yıldız Technical University, and 1 (1.0%) doctoral dissertation was conducted at each university. The rates of conversion of doctoral dissertations into publications are presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: The rates of conversion of dissertations into publication

As Figure 1 demonstrates, out of the 98 doctoral dissertations included in the research sample, 27 (28%) were not converted into any publication, while 71 (72%) were converted into publications. It is worth looking at the types of publications produced by doctoral dissertations. The publications produced from doctoral theses are categorized into three groups: books, book chapters and articles. The ratios of publications according to these groups are illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Types of publications extracted from dissertations

Figure 2 indicates that a total of 82 publications were produced from doctoral dissertations. Of these publications, 66 (81%) are articles, 10 (12%) are books and 6 (7%) are book chapters. It is apparent that articles are mostly preferred in the conversion of doctoral dissertations into publications. From some dissertations, more than one publication was produced. In the research, it was determined that two publications-two articles or one article and one book chapter-were produced from 9 doctoral dissertations, and three publications-two articles and one book chapter-were produced from one dissertation.

It was also determined that all of the doctoral dissertations that were converted into books or book chapters were published by international well-known publishers. Figure 3 presents the distribution of articles produced from dissertations according to indexes.

Figure 3: Distribution of articles by index

As shown in Figure 3, 40 (61%) of the articles produced from doctoral dissertations were published in journals indexed in the TR index, 18 (27%) in international indexes and 8 (12%) in international field indexes. It was determined that more than half of the articles were published in journals indexed in the TR index. The fact that no articles were encountered in journals indexed in SSCI, SCI, SCI-Expanded and AHCI indexes can be regarded as one of the striking findings of the research. The Selçuk University Journal of Faculty of Letters (f=3) and Journal

of Language and Linguistic Studies (f=2) were the most preferred journals in international field indexes. The journals indexed in the TR index in which the most articles are published are as follows: Journal of Bayburt Education Faculty (f=5), International Journal of Turkish Literature Culture Education (f=5), Turkish Studies (f=4), and Hacettepe University Journal of Turkish Studies (f=4). The journals indexed in international indexes in which the most articles are published are as follows: Mustafa Kemal University Journal of Social Sciences Institute (f=4) and International Journal of Languages' Education and Teaching (f=3).

In the Results section, summarize the collected data and the analysis performed on those data relevant to the discourse that is to follow. Report the data in sufficient detail to justify your conclusions. Mention all relevant results, including those that run counter to expectation; be sure to include small effect sizes (or statistically nonsignificant findings) when theory predicts large (or statistically significant) ones. Do not hide uncomfortable results by omission. Do not include individual scores or raw data with the exception, for example, of single-case designs or illustrative examples. In the spirit of data sharing (encouraged by APA and other professional associations and sometimes required by funding agencies), raw data, including study characteristics and individual effect sizes used in a meta-analysis, can be made available on supplemental online archives.

4. Discussion

In the present research, the rate of conversion of doctoral dissertations in the field of TTFL into publications, the type of publications, and the distribution of publications according to indexes were examined.

In this research, in which 98 doctoral dissertations in the field of TTFL were examined, the number of doctoral dissertations has experienced a significant increase since 2018. The years in which the most doctoral dissertations were completed in the data source were 2018 (f=21), 2019 (f=28) and 2020 (f=17). Therefore, as Seref & Karagöz (2020) point out, 2018 was an important milestone for the field. Kahtalı & Günata (2021), in their research analyzing postgraduate theses between 2014 and 2020, and Maden & Önal (2021), in their research analyzing the research trends of postgraduate theses in the related field between 2015 and 2020, reached similar results. However, Kahtalı & Günata (2021) found that 57 doctoral dissertations were completed between 2014 and 2020, and Maden & Önal (2021) found that 84 doctoral dissertations were completed between 2015 and 2020. This difference between the two studies can be explained by the use of different query terms. In this research, the fact that the data source consists of a total of 98 doctoral dissertations indicates that the representativeness of the research sample is quite high.

It was determined that doctoral dissertations in the field of TTFL were conducted in 19 different universities until 2020. According to the findings of the research, most theses were completed at Hacettepe University, Gazi University and Atatürk University. Maden & Önal (2021) found that postgraduate theses in the related field were conducted in 64 different universities between 2015 and 2020 and that these theses were mostly completed at Gazi University, Hacettepe University and Çanakkale Onsekiz Mart University. In the aforementioned research, it is seen that the number of universities is high since master's and doctoral dissertations are evaluated together. However, Hacettepe University and Gazi University ranked among the top universities in both studies. This can be interpreted by the fact that both universities have masters and doctoral programs in teaching Turkish as a foreign language.

One of the striking results of the research is that 27 doctoral dissertations were not converted into publications. This situation can be explained by the fact that some doctoral students may work in different educational institutions instead of pursuing an academic career within universities or that they cannot find a position at the universities. Negative experiences during doctoral education, lack of motivation, time or communication with the supervisor, personal or family matters and additional mentorship needs can all be other factors that may decrease the likelihood of publication of doctoral dissertations (Evans et al., 2018). New graduates may also underestimate the value of their dissertations. In this regard, supervisors should inspire graduates to produce publications, as doctoral dissertations are an original research and can contribute to disseminating into the scientific literature. However, especially with the increase in publications produced from dissertations completed in 2018, 2019, and

2020, it may be predicted that this number will decrease due to the long publication processes of articles in some journals.

In the research, it was revealed that articles, books and book chapters were the most preferred methods of converting doctoral theses into publications. The conversion time for all doctoral theses to all publications is calculated as a year and 5 months. The obligation to produce publications from graduate theses in associate professorship applications introduced by the Turkish Interuniversity Board and the obligation to publish before the thesis defense in some universities may be considered influential in the conversion of doctoral theses into publications. However, as Karagöz & Şeref (2021) point out, the production of publications from doctoral dissertations should not be seen solely as a means of meeting the criteria for promotion, and it is also important for young researchers to gain recognition and visibility.

Most of the articles are available online and are shorter than dissertations or books; in other words, they are reader-friendly and can contribute to the development of scientific literature faster in terms of reaching a much wider readership. Therefore, it can be argued that articles have a higher impact value than doctoral dissertations. Evans et al. (2018) detected in their research that articles produced from doctoral dissertations received higher citations than doctoral dissertations. Publication in a peer-reviewed journal also indicates that the content of the dissertation is acceptable to the international scientific community (Nieminen et al., 2007). In other words, they do not lack methodological rigor, including fatal flaws, or fail to make a novel, substantive and original contribution to the field (Evans et al., 2018). Ten doctoral dissertations in the research sample were converted into books published by international publishers. It can be claimed that the concern for academic promotion is at the forefront of the preferences of converting doctoral dissertations into publications for new graduates since high points in associate professorship applications are obtained from the book according to the criteria determined by the Interuniversity Board.

The majority of the articles produced from the thesis were published in journals indexed in the TR index (f=40) and international indexes (f=18). Another striking result of the research is that while the number of articles published in journals indexed in the field indexes is 8, no articles were published in journals indexed in SSCI, SCI, SCI-Expanded and AHCI indexes. Karagöz & Şeref (2021) analyzed doctoral dissertations completed between 1995 and 2020 in Turkish language teaching and concluded that the publications produced from thesis were mostly published as national articles in journals originating from Turkey and that the number of publications listed in the Web of Science (SSCI/ESCI/AHCI) citation index was quite low. Therefore, it is suggested that the quality of doctoral dissertations in the field of TTFL should be reviewed. Publication in internationally recognized journals should be encouraged.

In conclusion, all doctoral students should be encouraged and motivated to publish their dissertations by their supervisors, and the supervisors should support and guide them to contribute to disseminating into the scientific literature. It should not be forgotten that published dissertations may be a prideful event not only for doctoral graduates' careers but also for their supervisors and even for universities.

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